

Assessment of Knowledge and Attitude of Health Care Workers Regarding Continuous Professional Development Programs, Alexandria, Egypt

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Abstract:

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) refers to the educational pursuits that professionals make after completing their basic education and continues throughout their professional working lives in order to improve their knowledge, proficiency, and personal skills. CPD programs are crucial for enhancing the abilities of healthcare professionals and allowing them to provide patients with better care. However, few studies have discussed on this issue in Egypt. We conducted the current study to assess the knowledge and attitude of health care workers regarding CPD programs in a tertiary care hospital. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, Alexandria after the acceptance from Ethical Committee. The data were collected by interviewing

questionnaire from a purposive sample of thirty-two healthcare workers who are representative of stakeholder groups to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding continuous professional programs. The questionnaire consists of three divisions, the first one is concerned with personal data, second one covers the knowledge assessment, and the last one embraces the attitude evaluation section. The study lasted 3 months. Data were analyzed by using a suitable statistical software. We found that majority of the participants had good knowledge level (96.9%) and strongly positive attitude (75%) regarding CPD programs. In conclusion, the study findings demonstrated a significant level of knowledge and attitude of the participants regarding continuous professional programs which opens the way for further research that assess the implementation and standardization of CPD programs in the future.

Keywords: *Attitude, continuous professional development, knowledge.*

Introduction

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) refers to a period of education and training for health care workers (HCW) that begins after they complete their basic medical education and continues throughout their professional working lives (World Federation for Medical Education [WFME], 2003). CPD activities are classified into conference, symposium, training course, specialized workshop, scientific publication and review, general workshop, seminar, internal activity, and distance learning (Center for Continuing Education and Professional Development [CEPD], 2021). The main objective of CPD programs is to improve the efficiency and quality of HCWs to provide better service to patients (Center for Continuing Education and Professional Development [CEPD], 2021).

Several studies have been conducted to assess the effectiveness of CPD programs on HCW. For instance, a survey of geriatric physicians' satisfaction and availability for CPD was conducted in Australia; the findings showed that while on-campus training courses are beneficial to them, they require more flexible training courses to increase physician participation and meet their needs and expectations (Etherton-Ber et al., 2016). Wagner, a pre-and post-test was conducted to assess the impact of family medicine courses in KSA showed a positive impact on knowledge and skills of the participants (Al-Baghli et al., 2015) In addition, a cross sectional study was done at public hospitals, Douala, Cameroon reported that 98.0% of the nurses had ever heard of CPD, but only 59.9% could identify it (Ndang, E. A., 2022). One more study conducted on Scottish pharmacists' views and attitudes regarding CPD revealed four associated factors: "having positive support in the workplace, having access to resources and meeting learning needs, having confidence in the CPD process and motivation to participate in the CPD process"(Power et al., 2011).

Furthermore, another study was conducted in Lebanon to identify the views and assess motivation and attitudes of pharmacists towards

mandatory CPD has found that 55.4% felt confident that CPD meets their needs. (Saade et al., 2018). Because academic research on CPD in Egypt is sparse, we performed our study to assess Health Care Workers' Knowledge and Attitudes toward Continuous Professional Development Programs.

Methodology

Study Setting

The study was conducted at Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, HIO, Alexandria.

Study Design

Cross sectional study

Target Population

Health care workers who are representative of all departments of a selected hospital were included in the study till we reached to sample size.

Type of Sample

Non-random and purposive sample. The purposive sampling could be used when the researcher wants to discover, understand, and gain insight into a phenomenon (Merriam, 1998).

Sample Size and Method

The targets are representative of stakeholder groups, which affect and are affected by CPD. This includes, for example, department directors, specialists, consultants, GP, fellowship trainers, Residents, Nurses, and Frontline officers. Thirty-two health care workers were included in the study.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Numerical data were expressed as mean and standard deviation or median and range as appropriate. Qualitative data were expressed as frequency and percentage. Pearson's Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used to examine the relation between qualitative variables. For Knowledge and attitude score, comparison

between two groups was done using Mann-Whitney test (non-parametric t-test). Correlation between scores was tested using Spearman-rho correlation. All tests were two-tailed. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Data Collection Tools

The interviewing questionnaire was designed and developed by the researcher to gain information about the knowledge and attitude of HCW regarding the CPD program.

Questionnaire Validation

First, we established face validity. There were two important steps in this process. The first one was evaluating the questionnaire by experts who understand our topic to determine whether the questions effectively captured the topic under investigation. They checked the survey for common errors like double-barreled, confusing, and leading questions.

The second step was to perform a pilot study. A pilot study was done before gross data collection to ascertain the clarity and feasibility of the tool, to estimate the exact time needed for filling it up, and to detect any problems that might face the researcher and interfere with data collection. It entailed pretesting of the questionnaire on 3 participants which was not included in the final analysis. The respondents took an average of 15 minutes to answer the questionnaire, with a range of 12 to 18 minutes. The majority of respondents found the questionnaire easy to understand. A few items were reworded for clarity. Relevant modifications were instituted before the commencement of actual data collection.

We checked the internal consistency of questions loading onto the same factors. It is a measure of reliability in that it checks whether the responses are consistent. A standard test of internal consistency is Cronbach's Alpha (CA). Cronbach Alpha values range from 0 – 1.0. In present study, Cronbach Alpha value was 0.68 which is considered acceptable value.

The Questionnaire Included 3 Main Sections

The first part concerned with personal, professional, and qualified characteristics of participants such as name, age, gender, ID, previous experience, qualifications, specialty, position title, job status (permanent or contract), and past medical history.

The second one assessed the knowledge of participants regarding the CPD program through 10 yes/no questions, the correct answer was given a score of 1 and the wrong score was 0.

The third division assessed the attitude of participants toward the CPD program, a total of 10 statements representing positive and negative attitudes were administered to all respondents. For positive attitudes, the score was given 5 for strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for uncertain, 2 for disagree, and 1 for strongly disagree response. However, the reverse score was given to negative attitude statements.

The mean score of respondents: The mean score of respondents 1.00-1.79 was considered having a strongly negative attitude, 1.80-2.59: negative, 2.60-3.39: neutral, 3.40-4.19: positive, and lastly 4.20-5.00 was considered having a strongly positive attitude.

Results

The sociodemographic and professional characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1, it was found that half of the participants were in the age group of 40 years or older, the majority of respondents were female (75%), about three fourths were married, approximately one third had bachelor degree while, only 9% had diploma certificate, the nurse and pediatric specialty predominated and recorded 43.7%, and about 60% had experience for 15 years or more.

Table 1. Sociodemographic and Professional Factors of the Participants, (n = 32) (Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, 2023)

Sociodemographic and professional factors		Count	Column N %
Age	< 40 yrs	16	50.0%
	>= 40 years	16	50.0%
Gender	Male	8	25.0%
	Female	24	75.0%
Civil.status	Single	5	15.6%
	Married	23	71.9%
	Divorced	4	12.5%
Employment	Permanent	28	87.5%
	Contact	1	3.1%
	Delegated	3	9.4%
Education	Bachelor degree	12	37.5%
	Postgraduate diploma	7	21.9%
	Master degree	6	18.8%
	Ph.D. degree	4	12.5%
	Diploma	3	9.4%
Specialty	Surgery	1	3.1%
	Internal medicine	2	6.3%
	ENT	1	3.1%
	Pediatric	5	15.6%
	Medical record	1	3.1%
	Pharmacist	3	9.4%
	Neuropsychiatry	2	6.3%
	Chemist	2	6.3%
	Radiology Technician	1	3.1%
	Diagnostic Radiology	1	3.1%
	Dentist	1	3.1%
	Physiotherapist	3	9.4%
	Nurse Specialist	1	3.1%
	Nurse Supervisor	1	3.1%
	Nurse	7	21.9%
Position.title	GP	6	18.8%
	Specialist	4	12.5%
	Consultant	6	18.8%
	Nurse	9	28.1%
	Medical record officer	1	3.1%
	Pharmacist	3	9.4%
	Chemist	2	6.3%
	Radiology Technician	1	3.1%
Experience	< 15 years	13	40.6%
	>= 15 years	19	59.4%

Table 2 shows the findings of knowledge assessment regarding CPD programs; ten (yes/no) questions were used to assess the awareness of the participants about CPD. The results demonstrated that the median knowledge score was 9 (8-10) which mirrored a good level. We found that all the participants realized the right definition and activities of CPD programs and indicated that CPD activities should be documented. In the fourth, fifth, eighth, and

tenth questions, it was found that about 97% of the respondents agreed with the concepts of that CPD programs have positive role in enhancing knowledge, professional skills, practices, and reduced adverse events in health care facilities and that they are necessary for HCW promotions respectively. Last, 100% of the participants in sixth and ninth questions acknowledged that CPD programs could improve the educational department and that

they should include guidelines to explain the procedure. The total knowledge score was converted into levels, the current results demonstrated that about 96.9 % of the

participants had good knowledge level while, only 3.1% had a fair level as shown in figure (1).

**Table 2. Knowledge Assessment, (n = 32)
(Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, 2023)**

Knowledge assessment questions		Count	%
Q1. Participants know CPD definition	No	0	0.0%
	Yes	32	100.0%
Q2. The CPDP activities include conferences, workshops, seminars, and training courses.	No	0	0.0%
	Yes	32	100.0%
Q3. The CPD activity documentation is necessary.	yes	32	100.0%
	No	0	0.0%
Q4. The CPDP has a positive impact on the scientific knowledge of HCWs.	No	1	3.1%
	Yes	31	96.9%
Q5. CPDP has a positive impact on professional skills and HCW practice regarding patient care.	No	1	3.1%
	Yes	31	96.9%
Q6. CPDP implementation will improve the educational infrastructure tools.	No	0	0.0%
	Yes	32	100.0%
Q7. CPDP will enhance communication skills.	No	0	0.0%
	Yes	32	100.0%
Q8. A successful CPDP can reduce adverse events in hospitals.	No	1	3.1%
	Yes	31	96.9%
Q9. CPDP should include guidelines for recording activities.	No	0	0.0%
	Yes	32	100.0%
Q10. CPDP is mandatory for HCW promotions.	No	1	3.1%
	Yes	31	96.9%

**Figure 1. Knowledge Levels of Participants, (n = 32)
(Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, 2023)**

The attitude of participants was assessed by ten questions as shown in table (3). It was found that the median attitude score was 4.6 (3.8-5) which reflected strongly positive attitude. Regarding the first question, it was found that about half of

the participants (46.9%) did not accept that CPD programs as a bureaucratic process. The second question demonstrated that 90.6% of the participants agreed and strongly agreed that CPD is an enjoyable process. On the third and fourth questions, the results showed that more than three fourths of respondents (81.35%) strongly agreed on the concept that CPD programs are necessary for professional life and patient safety. Approximately two thirds (68.8%) strongly agreed with a belief that CPD programs are mandatory for career progression. Three fourths of participants believed that CPD programs are rewarding while, only 3.1% strongly accorded with that CPD is threatening and unnecessary. Lastly, we found that more than 90% of the participants agreed and strongly agreed with the faith that indicated that CPD programs enhance patient outcome and practical skills of health care workers. The present results demonstrated that 75% of the HCWs had strongly positive attitude as shown in figure (2).

**Table 3. Attitude Assessment, (n = 32)
(Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, 2023)**

Attitude assessment questions		Count	%
Q1. CPDP is a bureaucratic process	Strongly Agree	1	3.1%
	Agree	1	3.1%
	Uncertain	4	12.5%
	Disagree	15	46.9%
	Strongly Disagree	11	34.4%
Q2. CPDP is enjoyable	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Uncertain	3	9.4%
	Agree	17	53.1%
	Strongly Agree	12	37.5%
Q3. CPDP is a necessary part of professional life	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Uncertain	0	0.0%
	Agree	6	18.8%
	Strongly Agree	26	81.3%
Q4. CPDP is necessary for patient safety	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	1	3.1%
	Uncertain	1	3.1%
	Agree	4	12.5%
	Strongly Agree	26	81.3%
Q5. CPDP is mandatory for career progression	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Uncertain	1	3.1%
	Agree	9	28.1%
	Strongly Agree	22	68.8%
Q6. CPDP is rewarding	Strongly Disagree	2	6.3%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Uncertain	6	18.8%
	Agree	12	37.5%
	Strongly Agree	12	37.5%
Q7. CPDP is threatening	Strongly Agree	1	3.1%
	Agree	1	3.1%
	Uncertain	5	15.6%
	Disagree	9	28.1%
	Strongly Disagree	16	50.0%
Q8. CPDP is unnecessary	Strongly Agree	1	3.1%
	Agree	0	0.0%
	Uncertain	0	0.0%
	Disagree	9	28.1%
	Strongly Disagree	22	68.8%
Q9. CPDP improves patient outcome	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	1	3.1%
	Uncertain	1	3.1%
	Agree	9	28.1%
	Strongly Agree	21	65.6%
Q10. CPDP improved practical skills	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Uncertain	1	3.1%
	Agree	7	21.9%
	Strongly Agree	24	75.0%

Figure 2. Attitude levels of the Participants, (n = 32) (Sporting Tertiary Care Hospital, 2023)

We tested the relationship between the median knowledge and attitude scores, and socio demographic and professional characteristics, we found that there was not statistically significant association between knowledge or attitude and any of the sociodemographic and professional factors of the participants as shown in tables (4) and (5).

Table 4. Association of Median Knowledge Score with Sociodemographic and Professional factors

Sociodemographic and professional factors		Median	Minimum	Maximum	p-value
Age	< 40 years	9.0	8.0	9.0	0.752
	>= 40 years	9.0	7.0	9.0	
Gender	Male	9.0	8.0	9.0	0.881
	Female	9.0	7.0	9.0	
Civil.statu s	Unmarried	9.0	7.0	9.0	0.433
	Married	9.0	8.0	9.0	
Employ ment	Permanent	9.0	7.0	9.0	0.763
	Contact, delegated	9.0	9.0	9.0	
Educatio n	Bachelor degree	9.0	8.0	9.0	0.924
	Postgraduate, Master, PhD, diploma	9.0	7.0	9.0	
Specialty	Clinical	9.0	7.0	9.0	0.163
	Non clinical	9.0	9.0	9.0	
	Nurse	9.0	9.0	9.0	
Position.t itle	GP, Sp, Con	9.0	7.0	9.0	0.202
	Ph, Ch, MR	9.0	9.0	9.0	
	Nurse	9.0	9.0	9.0	
Experien ce	< 15 years	9.0	8.0	9.0	0.880
	>= 15 years	9.0	7.0	9.0	

Table 5. Association of the Median Attitude Score with Sociodemographic and Professional Factors

Sociodemographic and professional factors		Median	Minimum	Maximum	p-value
Age	< 40 years	4.7	3.8	5.0	0.196
	>= 40 years	4.5	3.7	5.0	
Gender	Male	4.6	3.9	4.9	0.949
	Female	4.5	3.7	5.0	
Civil status	Unmarried	4.7	3.9	5.0	0.301
	Married	4.5	3.7	5.0	
Employment	Permanent	4.5	3.7	5.0	0.332
	Contact, delegated	4.7	4.4	4.9	
Education	Bachelor's degree	4.4	3.7	5.0	0.716
	Postgraduate, Master, PhD, diploma	4.5	3.8	5.0	
Specialty	Clinical	4.5	3.9	5.0	

	Nonclinical	4.4	3.7	5.0	
	Nurse	4.5	3.8	4.9	0.955
Position title	GP, Sp, Con	4.5	3.9	5.0	
	Ph, Ch, MR	4.5	3.7	5.0	
	Nurse	4.5	3.8	4.9	0.910
Experience	< 15 years	4.6	3.8	5.0	
	>= 15 years	4.5	3.7	5.0	0.270

Discussion

We included 32 participants of HCWs in our study. The current study reported that 100% of the participants were able to correctly identify CPD programs and activities which is higher than that of a cross sectional study was in public hospitals at Douala Cameroon public hospital which assessed the knowledge, attitude, and practice of clinical nurses towards continuing professional development which reported that only 59.9% could identify it. (Ndang, E. A., 2022). This result suggests that the Egyptian HCWs had excellent background about CPD programs which represented a cornerstone in motivating them to share in CPD activities. The present results showed that more than 90% of the participants agreed and strongly agreed on the faith which indicated that CPD programs enhanced patient outcome and practical skills and approximately two thirds (68.8%) strongly agreed with a belief that CPD programs are mandatory for career progression which accords with the results of Canadian study which demonstrated that CPD had a positive impact on the clinical practice of family medicine. High quality and quantity CME has a positive correlation with the clinical practice of family medicine physicians (Goulet et al., 2013).

The current findings showed that the participants had good knowledge level and strongly positive attitude regarding CPD programs which aligned with a study from Cameroon which found adequate knowledge, awareness and positive perception towards CPD among clinical nurses in public hospitals in Douala, however, the participation in CPD programs was limited. (Ndang, E. A., 2022). This result showed the necessity to implement several convenient CPD programs for motivated HCWs in the future.

Limitations

The sample was purposive type and lacked randomization. The data collection was based on reporting from HCWs which could generate reporting bias. However, the study provided valuable information about awareness and direction of HCWs toward CPD programs.

Conclusion

The study findings demonstrated that the participants had good level of knowledge and strongly positive attitude toward continuous professional development programs which implied the need to implement well-structured and convenient CPD programs for HCWs. Further research will be required in the future to assess the effectiveness and standardization of CPD programs.

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Data availability

The datasets used and analyzed during the current study are available from the first author upon reasonable request.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

The researcher fulfilled the approval of the Ethics Committee of Ministry of Health and approval from Health Insurance Organization, Egypt, for conducting the study.

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